

EFFECT OF COVID-19 PANDEMICS ON ECONOMIC GROWTH IN NIGERIA

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17630129>

Abstract: This study is targeted to determine the effect of Covid-19 pandemic on economic growth in Nigeria. The study is guided by the following specific objectives which are; to determine the impact of Covid-19 pandemics on economic growth in Nigeria, to ascertain the causality relationship between Covid-19 pandemics and economic growth in Nigeria. The study adopted Ex post facto research design. The study build a multiple regression model, using real gross domestic product as the dependent variable whereas sample tested, infected cases, recoveries and death rate as the independent variables. The findings of the study reveals that sample tested, infected cases and recoveries rate have significant impact on the economic growth in Nigeria whereas death rate has no significant impact on the economic growth in Nigeria. More so, the study further concludes that all the variables under study (sample tested, infected cases and death rate) have negative relationship on the economic growth which implies that an increase in the study explanatory variables will lead to decrease in the economic growth on the average. The study recommended that World health organization, Nigeria centre for disease control, and all concerned governments and non-governmental organizations should sustain the efforts being used to create awareness and knowledge about preventive measures against Covid-19 among the masses because it is effective.
Key Words: Covid-19 Pandemics, Economic Growth, Infected cases, recovery cases, death rate and sample tested.

INTRODUCTION

The World was perplexed by the outbreak of the Coronavirus pandemic. COVID-19 is a pandemic with potentially serious health implications. It is a health challenge for our modern societies and health systems. The consequences of a pandemic for our global economy and financial sector are unprecedented (Adhikari, 2020).

The covid-19 started in Wuhan, Hubei Province, China, and the residents who lived in Wuhan had some links to large seafood and live animal markets, implying that animals transmitted the disease to human beings. The virus,

when first detected, was named "SARS-CoV-2" and later, "coronavirus disease of 2019" (abbreviated "Covid-19"). The first known case-patient of coronavirus started experiencing symptoms in Wuhan, China, in 2019, precisely, on the 1st December, and since then, there have been over 800,000 reported cases around the World. According to WHO, the disease was reported first in the city of Wuhan, China, in December 2019 (Adhikari, 2020). In other words, the disease has become a global pandemic. The pandemic has caused massive economic disruptions across the globe. Monetary experts have predicted that the pandemic could plunge the World into a worldwide recession (Ozili, 2020). Also, the pandemic has claimed a significant number of lives across the globe. The pandemic has negatively affected various sectors of the economy, such as education, banking, manufacturing, sports, agricultural, aviation, transportation, and hospitality. For example, in the aviation sector, the pandemic has led to massive cancellation of flights. The ban on international travel has prevented people from travelling abroad for business and personal purposes. The hospitality industry has also received its fair share of the effects of the pandemic. Many hotels have been closed down due to the lockdown policy, and their operations, sales, and profits would be affected negatively. Many hotel reservations were cancelled.

The COVID-19 pandemic, according to the International Monetary Fund (2021), has placed Nigeria at a critical juncture for some reasons: First, trends of de-carbonisation and the green economy and the subdued global recovery are expected to keep prices of oil at low rates; and secondly because of expected sluggish growth of non-oil sectors. While the Nigerian economy is diversified in terms of production, it is far from diversified in terms of earnings and revenue generation (Proshare, 2020). The export structure of the country, over the past decades, has fundamentally remained the same as 90 percent of the country's exports are still accounted for by hydrocarbon products (IMF, 2021). With fragmented exchange rates and loss in value of the naira relative to the US dollar, the current system creates uncertainties not just for the government but also for the other major agents that facilitate the economy. These are households, the private sector and the apex institution (Inegbedion, 2021). The extent to which these agents can efficiently and effectively carry out their roles has implications on the Nigerian economy (Inegbedion, 2021).

One of the implications of the COVID-19 crisis in Nigeria is that it unraveled longstanding unsustainable practices, economic deprivation and inequalities in our societies that pre-date the outbreak of the virus and have intensified its impact. Consequently, the major economic agents, including the government and the private sector institutions all have important roles to play in facilitating economic recovery in the country. With respect to the government, interventions meant to protect small businesses and households have been prioritized with the launch of the Nigerian economic sustainability plan in July 2020 with a number of recovery plans, including palliatives for MSMEs, discounts and waivers for small scale industries and artisans, among others (PWC, 2020; World Resources Institute, 2021). The recovery plans also include investments in infrastructure, public works, agriculture, and the clean energy subsector where about \$619 million is committed to the Solar Homes Systems Project, which is aimed at serving about 25 million individual Nigerians and up to 5 million households (War Risk Insurance, 2021).

At the level of the household, unemployment rates are higher for Nigerian youths. Without the means to earn an income in some sectors of the economy during the lockdown, many have fallen into extreme poverty (World Health Organisation, 2020). Although this has triggered temporary relief packages from the government and the easing of certain business regulations and laws, it also should lead to a review of other policies that undermine the friendliness of the business environment and ease of doing business factors. Such policies should aim at improving the formalization and standardization of MSMEs and consumer protection in Nigeria.

Reforms should also consider policies that encourage public-private sector collaborations and social innovations. Many of the current policies are aimed at absorbing the shocks induced by the pandemic. However, an economy that seeks to recover and build resilience should be one that puts innovation and creativity at the centre of its goal. As vaccine rollout is gradually gaining pace in Nigeria, issues around cost, availability and vaccine distribution, especially where cold storage is needed, give the impression that full national coverage is unlikely in the country in the next few years. This will ultimately delay the complete lifting of certain restrictions related to the pandemic (World Bank Group, 2021). Recovering better from these challenges will require innovation and solidarity (United Nation, 2021). This means improving the lives of the most marginalized and making the right fiscal and macroeconomic choices that will help close the inequality gap and place people's hard work and their creative and innovative abilities at the centre of recovery.

Statement of the Problem

The world is experiencing and expecting the deepest global recession due to the pandemic, as suggested by the World Bank (World Bank, 2020). As if this was less, different parts of the world are witnessing other natural and human-made hazards, making the scenario even worse. Australian bush fire, floods in Indonesia and India, a volcano eruption in the Philippines, earthquakes in Turkey, Iran, Russia, India, and Beirut blast, inter alia (Karamti & Abd- Mouleh, 2022; Kostis, 2021; Monteiro, 2020). These consequences of hazards are in addition to the pandemic that different countries are trying to fight. Nigeria, for that matter, had been trying to uplift its economy, which is now expected to fall back even deeper as most of the population depends on oil as a source of income (Lateef & Keikhosrokiani, 2022).

In addition, the pandemic has reduced traveling opportunities and, by extension, the use of oil and gas associated with the underlying opportunities. Not only Nigeria, but the entire world is facing or expected to face an economic crisis. Nigeria, a mono-economy (significant dependency on a single source: oil), has suffered a significant economic setback since the pandemic outbreak. This economic crisis has forced most of the population (as the majority is below the poverty line) of Nigeria to keep stepping out for work during the pandemic, not least, because hunger, compared to the novel corona virus, is a more direct cause of death (Egbunike, 2020; Diop and Asongu, 2021).

A World Bank (2020) report highlighted the effect of the pandemic on Nigeria with the following headline: 'Nigeria's Economy faces worst recessions in four decades.' Nigeria has been struggling with the economic crisis, and the arrival of COVID-19 has worsened the situation. Nigeria was once known for its agricultural produce with exports of palm produce, cocoa, rubber, timber, and groundnuts, inter alia (Kemi, 2016). However, 1956

marked the discovery of crude oil in Nigeria and gave rise to an excellent entrepreneurial opportunity. People started shifting from agriculture, the primary source of income generation then, to oil-related businesses. The economy experienced growth with the entrepreneurial initiative (Tchamyu, 2017), although excessive exploitation of this resource has led to water pollution in Nigeria (Okorie, 2018). Over the years, Nigeria depended solely on crude oil to drive its economy. Oil production also went down a couple of years ago when restiveness and agitation in the oil sector reached the Niger Delta region (Tiba and Frikha, 2020; Uduji et al., 2019a, b). With this announcement and restiveness, specific measures were proactively examined, including diversification of the economy from oil to agriculture (Ngouhou and Nchofoung, 2021).

From the chart above, it can be ascertained that as the number of sample tested is increasing, the number of the death rate is equally increasing alongside indicating an upward projection. The outbreak of Covid-19 in Nigeria is alarming, there are 176,747563 confirmed cases, 160801403 recoveries from the illness and 3820197 deaths worldwide as of June, 14th 2022 (Worldometers, 2022). On February 27, 2020, an Italian citizen became the index case for COVID-19 in Nigeria and as at June 14th, 2022, there were 167,066 laboratory-confirmed cases of COVID-19 in Nigeria with 163469 discharges and 2117 deaths (Nigeria Centre for Disease Control, NCDC, 2022).

Further, whenever the word 'crisis' comes up, 'management' follows because from survival to evolution, it all requires management. Crisis management is viewed as being ready for the possible risks which may arise due to the uncertainties by devising the action plan for different stages of crisis management, notably, pre-crisis, during the crisis, post-crisis (Ansell and Boin, 2019; Herbane, 2013). However, Schadet al. (2016) suggested that one could be prepared for only the probable (estimated) problems, while some crises suddenly ambush individuals, businesses, and the economy. Today's COVID-19 pandemic scenario is a true example of sudden health and economic crises, emphasizing the fact that not all crises allow us the time to be prepared to face them, and

suddenly we are left surrounded by the underlying crises (Al- Dabbagh, 2020). Since we are still in crisis and the full impact of the pandemic is yet not measurable, it is essential to have a diagnostic approach as well as a prescriptive approach for dealing with the ‘during crisis’ and ‘post-crisis stages of the present scenario. The factors leading to the adverse economic crisis are pointed out in this article, and measures that can help cope with the crisis are discussed. The two approaches will further assist in drawing a change management model of how entrepreneurship could be best practiced, beating Nigeria’s economic crisis by bringing an entrepreneurial change.

This study focuses on Nigeria as a mono-economic nation, a case of how it could overcome economic instability and stay afloat in times of economic crisis, which has worsened due to the ongoing COVID-19. The Prescriptive approach aims at understanding and analyzing the reasons for continuing and upcoming complications, the available resources, and their usefulness to tackle these complications to utilize them and finally devising a conceptual model to curb the barriers of entrepreneurial innovativeness- the ultimate solution of the economic crisis in Nigeria. The diagnostic approach would lead us to a prescriptive discovery steering that in the prevalent crisis, industries could be tapped upon for entrepreneurial innovativeness given the current status of factors worsening the economic crisis. The worsening economic status of Nigeria is viewed as a result of innovative- and entrepreneurship-resistant policies, strategies, and practices prevalent in the region.

Research Questions

This study will be guided by the following research questions:

- i. What is the impact of Covid-19 pandemics on the economic growth in Nigeria?
- ii. What is the causality relationship between Covid-19 pandemics and economic growth in Nigeria?

Objectives of the Study

The broad objective of the study is to examine the effect of Covid-19 pandemic on economic growth in Nigeria; specifically, this study tends to:

- i. Determine the impact of Covid-19 pandemics on economic growth in Nigeria.
- ii. Ascertain the causality relationship between Covid-19 pandemics and economic growth in Nigeria.

Hypotheses of the Study

- i. **H₀:** Covid-19 pandemics has no significant impact on the economic growth in Nigeria.
- ii. **H₀:** There is no causality relationship between Covid-19 pandemics and economic growth in Nigeria.

Scope of Study

This study is focused on the Covid-19 pandemics and economic growth in Nigeria. The study will be limited to Nigerian economy. The effect of the Covid-19 pandemics will be reviewed and relevant variables will be adopted for the study. In the course of this study, real gross domestic product (RGDP) will be used to capture economic growth which will stand as the dependent variable whereas sample tested (ST), infected cases (IC), Recoveries (RC) and death rate (DR) will serve as the independent variables. The choice of these variables is because they stand as reliable indicators of the research topic. The period covered in this work is monthly data within the time frame of 2020-2022

LITERATURE REVIEW

Conceptual Literature

Concept of COVID-19 Pandemic

Coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) is defined as illness caused by a novel coronavirus now called severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2; formerly called 2019-nCoV), which was first identified amid an outbreak of respiratory illness cases in Wuhan City, Hubei Province, China (WHO, 2020). It was initially reported to the WHO on December 31, 2019. On January 30, 2020, the WHO declared the COVID-19 outbreak a global health emergency. On March 11, 2020, the WHO declared COVID-19 a global pandemic, its first such designation since declaring H1N1 influenza a pandemic in 2009.

Before the advent of this present pandemic, the world had some experiences of coronavirus in the past. The two most recent experiences, the Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome, which happened in China in 2002, 2003 and the Middle-East Respiratory Syndrome, which occurred in some Middle East and some other countries outside the Middle-East in 2012 (Zhong, 2003). However, Previous Coronaviruses did not cause devastating consequences. They caused “mild infections in immunocompromised people and were not considered to be highly pathogenic in humans until they circulated in the Guangdong province of China in 2002 and 2003 during the Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome (SARS) outbreak” (Zhong, 2003). The cumulative number of infections recorded was 8437. Out of this number, 813 (9.6%) of the cases were fatal while 7452 (90.4%) of the cases recovered (WHO, 2023).

Another wave of coronavirus known as the Middle East respiratory syndrome was experienced between 2012 and 2013. “The first documented cases of MERS occurred in Jordan in early 2012. Globally, to date, there has been a total of 55 cases confirmed by laboratory testing.

Out of these, 40 have occurred in KSA, and the rest have been reported from other countries in the Middle East (Qatar and the United Arab Emirates), from Tunisia in North Africa, and France, Germany, Italy and the United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland in Europe” (WHO, 2013). Despite having a limited number of cases, the death rate of MERS was about sixty per cent (60%) (WHO, 2013). Thus, the combined cases of infections from SARS and MERS amounted to 8492.

The coronavirus, also known as COVID-19, which began in China in 2019, was linked to a novel Coronavirus that was named SARS-CoV-2 (Zhu, 2020). It is pertinent to note that “the new strain of coronavirus had not been previously identified in humans and the disease associated with it has been dubbed Coronavirus diseases 2019 (COVID-19) by the WHO (Bawazir et al., 2020). The virus has spread to over 155 countries, causing severe morbidity and mortality since its emergence in 2019 (Wu, 2020). However, as of 14th May 2020, the world had witnessed five million, one hundred and three thousand, and six (5, 103, 006) cases of COVID-19 (following the applied case definitions and testing strategies in the affected countries), including 109, 536 fatalities, representing 2.15% of the infections (WHO, 2020). The results also indicate that 74,256 of the infections are from Africa,

182,278 are from South East Asia, and 2,282,488 are from America, as well as 1,987,657 from Europe and 172,696 from Western Pacific, among others. The fatalities associated with the different continents as of 14th May 2020 were 2504 (Africa), 5119 (South-East Asia), 62,221 (America) and 21,413 (Europe).

As of October 2021; barely one year after the commencement of the COVID-19 pandemic, the total confirmed cases rose to 34,804,348 with 1,030,738 (2.96%) fatalities globally (WHO, 2020). This partly explains why COVID-19 appears to have attracted more global attention in terms of sensitisation and lockdowns than the previous cases.

Concept of Economic Growth

Black (2022) defines economic growth as the increase in economic variable, normally persisting over successive periods. According to Anyanwu (2025), economic growth is defined as “the increase overtime of an economy’s capacity to produce those goods and services needed to improve the well-being of the citizens in increasing numbers and diversity”. According to Todaro (2017), it is the steady process through which the productive capacity of the economy is increased over time. Economic growth is also a study in macroeconomics. It is on the basis of macroeconomics that the resources and the capability of an economy are evaluated; plans for overall increase in national income, output, and employment are framed and implemented so as to raise the level of economic development of the economy.

Harrod and Domar (1958) assign a key role to investment in the process of economic growth, but they lay emphasis on the dual nature of investment, first it creates income and secondly it augments the productive capacity of the economy by increasing its capital stock. The former may be regarded as the demand effect and the latter the supply effect of investment. Solow builds his model of economic growth as an alternative to the Harrod-Domar line of thought without its crucial assumption of fixed proportions in production, Solow postulates a continuous production function linking output to the inputs of capital and labour which are sustainable.

Growth is equally seen as meaningful if there is an improvement in the well-being of the populace overtime, which can be possible if the rate of population growth lags behind that of economic growth, Domar (1958). And as Thabo Mbeki puts it; “Economic growth can only transfer to economic development if the proceeds of growth are equitably distributed”.

The Nigeria experience of COVID-19 pandemic

The COVID-19 pandemic in Nigeria is part of the worldwide pandemic of Coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) caused by severe acute respiratory syndrome Coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2). The first confirmed case in Nigeria was announced on 27 February 2020 (Radio Network News, 2020), when an Italian citizen in Lagos tested positive for the virus. On 9 March 2020, a second case of the virus was reported in Ewekoro, Ogun State, and a Nigerian citizen who had contact with the Italian citizen.

However, there has been a total number of 64,184 confirmed cases, 1,156 deaths with 60,069 discharged cases carried out across the 36 states of the country as of 10th November, 2020. Lagos state has proven to be the epicentre of the outbreak in Nigeria with 21,960 cases and 220 deaths, while Kogi state has recorded the lowest number in the country with 5 cases with no deaths (Daily News, 20th October, 2020).

In Nigeria, President Muhammadu Buhari in two successive broadcasts to the nation ordered a lockdown of certain parts of the country such as Abuja, Lagos and Ogun State. Mr Buhari also ordered the restriction of human and vehicular movements across the country. The ban on movement and travelling also affected the consumption of petroleum products. In Nigeria, due to the drop in oil price, the budget review proposal has been sent to the Senate for approval, with a 39% slash in the original budget.

The manufacturing sectors were badly hit in the pandemic; due to lockdown and quarantine rules as working from home is not a feasible option for this aspect of the economy and limitations in importation being a barrier, especially in countries like Nigeria whose manufacturing industries are hugely dependent on the importation of raw materials especially from China (David, 2020). A reduction of 1.2% production is predicted in the global chemical industry; their worst growth since the financial crash of 2008. The tertiary sector such as the education sectors, finance sectors, hospitality and tourism sectors, sports industry, media and information industry, real estate and housing industry and so on continue to feel the brunt of the pandemic outbreak. Closure of all schools including primary, secondary and tertiary institutions is one of the major recommendations advised to limit the spread of COVID-19, as school gathering has been proven to be a major means of disease spread during outbreaks.

While most advanced nations are developing the use of new technology such as e-learning platforms, such cannot be fully implemented in Nigeria, due to the divide in the educational system whereby certain services cannot be accessed by people in poor rural settings and some in urban settings (Solomon, 2020).

In Nigeria, the federal government sent a revised budget to the National Assembly due to constant drop in crude oil prices, and thereby revised the budget proposal revenue projection for the 2020 fiscal period by a difference of ₦3.3 trillion from the initially approved amount of ₦8.41 trillion to ₦5.08 trillion. Meanwhile, amid the partial lockdown of the country, economic activities at the macro and micro levels have been grounded, while social activities are also halted. The above situations have forced governments, both at the state and federal levels to put in place some palliative measures to cushion the effects on the masses and businesses.

Health Behavior in Pandemic

For different risks, the public could take preventive actions accordingly. During the pandemic, governments and health care institutions issued guidelines for prevention. However, there are differences in these guidelines in different countries and regions. In this study, the recommendation behaviors issued by Chinese official health care institutions were adopted as standards of preventive behavior (David, 2020). Additionally, some people in the Chinese mainland implemented personal protective measures beyond the recommended standards. However, because of the practical limitations (such as the shortage of N95 face masks at the early stage of the pandemic, giving priority to the needs of medical staff), these measures may not be implemented or may only be people's intention (Semetko, 2020).

Some behavior theories have also been applied in health communication to identify factors affecting decision-making for public health behavior. The representative ones are the health belief model (HBM), extended parallel process model (EPPM), the theory of planned behavior (TPB) and social cognitive theory, etc. These theories

extend their application in empirical studies on public health emergencies, including SARS, Ebola, MERS, and influenza. Although these theories try to describe the change of health behavior from different perspectives, they generally share the core concept that individual factors can influence and maintain the decisions on health behavior, provided that information is available (Stockton, 2020). Particularly, the individual's social psychology has a direct or indirect impact on health behavior. These variables are classified into three dimensions in meta-theory of health communication: (a) cognitive factors, including perceived risk, subjective norms, attitudes, self-image, and self-efficacy; (b) emotional factors, covering fear, sadness, affection, pleasure, trust, and empathy; and (c) social context factors, involving mutual understanding, cohesion and reciprocity, and collective efficacy. The effects of three factors on health behavior are complementary and accumulative (Oleribe, 20150).

Effect of Covid-19 Outbreak on Economic Welfare in Nigeria

The outbreak of COVID-19 pandemic caused by severe acute respiratory syndrome (SARS) was confirmed in Nigeria 27th February 2020 following the incident of an Italian citizen who tested positive for the virus in Lagos. This reported case led to increase in panic which took its toll when a second case was confirmed and reported on 9th March 2020 in Ogun State Nigeria. From this moment there has been different reported cases ranging from deaths, recoveries, new cases and new deaths which have affected economic activities in Nigeria and consequently, the welfare of her people (Obiozor, 2020).

Nigeria is an oil dependent country and among the first countries in Sub-Saharan Africa to witness the outbreak of Covid-19. The outbreak of corona virus and the consequence of the strict measures initiated to checkmate the spread of the virus affected international oil prices which plummeted by 60% following the global tension due to the pandemic. Hence, it is obvious that oil sector is the leading sector in Nigeria, and account for more than 70% of revenue in Nigeria. Thus, the fall in oil prices raises so much concern to the authorities and policy makers (Ogbodo, 2018). This has caused the government and her citizens and the implications have resulted to hardship due to high cost of living, poor standard of living, and high increase in food inflation, and fall consumer spending owing to poor purchasing of the households in the face of high consumer price index resulting to lose of consumers' confidence. Thus, alleviating the threat of Covid-19 crisis is important to prevent the deepening of poverty from its usual state in Nigeria. It is evident that before the outbreak, nearly 4 out of 10 Nigerians were below the poverty line, and the larger population (in millions) were slightly above the poverty line, thereby increasing the likelihood of falling back into poverty.

COVID-19 Lockdown and Economic Activities

Spillovers from the COVID-19 pandemic precipitated a decline in demand for oil products as well as constrained economic activities following the enforcement of the physical distancing policies (Ozili, 2020b). The degree of economic crises caused by the COVID-19 pandemic is unprecedented; there is no doubt that it has left dramatic rippling effects across the global economy, significantly constraining the level of economic activities in every region of the world (Copenhagen Economics, 2020). The COVID-19 pandemic has so far had its toll on economic activities and there seems to be no end in sight for now. This has led to a significant impact on social policies as

well as the social and economic well-being of citizens, especially the drastic reduction in economic activities (Ozili, 2020).

Theoretical Literature

Theory of Covid-19 Pandemic

Health Believe Model

The theoretical framework of this study is anchored on health believe model by Rosenstock in 1950. According to the theory, the prevention of health related illness depends largely on age, gender, ethnicity and age (Rosentock, 1974). The theory maintains that demographic and socio-economic characteristics could be modified through education but it is still a hypotheses which is yet to be proved right or wrong.

The theory indicates that believes a human characteristics which shape peoples behavior and pattern of life. If persuasive techniques can be used to change behaviour-related beliefs and such interventions result in behaviour change, this provides a theoretical and practical basis for evidence-based health education.

Beliefs are also modifiable and can differentiate between individuals from the same background.

The health believe model suggest that characteristics such as socio-economic status, gender, ethnicity, and age were known to be associated with preventive health-related behaviour patterns. The health believe model assumes that the influence of Covid-19 awareness campaign on the social distancing behavior of Nigeria students depends on the individual health related believe.

Receptive Theory

Receptive theory is a version of reader response literary theory that emphasizes each particular reader's reception or interpretation in making meaning from a literary text. Receptive theory is generally referred to as audience receptive in the analysis of communications models. In literary studies, receptive theory originated from the work of Hans-Robert Jauss in the late 1960s, and the most influential work was produced during the 1970s and early 1980s in Germany and the US (Fortier 132), with some notable work done in other Western European countries. A form of receptive theory has also been applied to the study of historiography.

The cultural theorist Stuart Hall was one of the main proponents of receptive theory, first developed in his 1973 essay 'Encoding and Decoding in the Television Discourse'. His approach, called the encoding/decoding model of communication, is a form of textual analysis that focuses on the scope of "negotiation" and "opposition" by the audience. This means that a "text"—be it a book, movie, or other creative work—is not simply passively accepted by the audience, but that the reader/viewer interprets the meanings of the text based on her or his individual cultural background and life experiences. In essence, the meaning of a text is not inherent within the text itself, but is created within the relationship between the text and the reader.

Receptive theory has since been extended to the spectators of performative events, focusing predominantly on the theatre. Susan Bennett is often credited with beginning this discourse. Receptive theory has also been applied to the history and analysis of landscapes, through the work of the landscape historian John Dixon Hunt, as Hunt recognized that the survival of gardens and landscapes is largely related to their public reception.

Theories of Economic Growth

Harrod-Domar Growth Model

According to Harrod (1946) the principal strategies of development is mobilisation of domestic and foreign saving in order to generate sufficient investment to accelerate economic growth. The economic mechanism by which more investment leads to more growth can be described in terms of Harrod-Domar growth model, often referred to as the AK model. Every economy must save a certain proportion of its national income to be used to replace worn out or impaired capital goods (depreciations provision). For a country to grow new investment representing net addition to capital stock is important, believing that there is a direct relationship between the size of the total capital stock K and total gross domestic product (GDP).

According to Rostow (1956), the countries that were able to save 15% to 20% of GNP could grow at a much faster rate than those that saved less. Moreover, this growth would then be self-sustained. The mechanisms of economic growth and development, therefore, are simply a matter of increasing national savings and investment. The main obstacle or constraint on development, according to this theory, was the relatively low level of new capital formation in most poor countries. But if a country wanted to grow at, let say, a rate of 7% per annum and if it could not generate savings and investment at a rate of 21% (i.e., $7\% \times 3$) of national income but could not only manage to save 15%, it could seek to fill this saving gap of 6% through either foreign aid or private foreign investment (Isola, 2013).

Keynesian Theory

In 1936, John Maynard Keynes wrote the book “The general Theory of employment, Interest and Money” which established the foundation of Keynesianism. Keynesians believes on the intervention of government to reach full production. They believe that intervention in economy by government through expansionary economic policies will boost investment and promote demand to reach full production. The Keynesian model is based on Aggregate Demand (AD) and Aggregate Supply (AS) curves. In this model AS curve is upward sloping in the short run so that the change in the demand side of the economy affects both price and output.

Dornbusch, (1996) also argues that AD and AS yields an adjustment path. It shows an initial positive relationship between inflation and economic growth but eventually turns negative towards the latter part of the adjustment path. The initial positive relationship between inflation and economic growth is due to the time inconsistency problem. Producers feel that only the prices of their products have increased while the other producers are operating at the same price level. However, in reality overall prices have increased. Therefore, the producer continues more and more output¹. Moreover, Blanchard and Kiyotaki (1987) said inflation and economic growth are positively related because of the agreement of firms to supply on agreed price. So the firm has to produce even at increased price. Later on the relationship becomes negative. This describes phenomena of stagflation that is output decreases or remains the same when price rises.

Empirical Review

Ozili (2020) examined COVID-19 in Africa: Socio-economic impact, policy response and opportunities in Africa. The design employed was discourse analysis. The broad objective of the study is to examine the impact of Covid-

19 pandemics in Africa. The results show that the coronavirus pandemic has had a significant effect on African countries. The pandemic is having its toll on economic activities and social interaction through the safety measures put in place to curtail the pandemic, such as physical distancing. The study adopted ex post factor research design and multiple regression analyses to examine the socio economic impact of Covid-19 pandemic in sub-saharan Africa. A major implication of the study is the influence of social policies on the social and economic well-being of citizens, especially the drastic reduction in economic activities.

Teachout and Zipfel (2020) examined the economic impact of COVID-19 lockdowns in sub-Saharan Africa, they sought to quantify the impact of lockdowns on people's livelihoods. Consistent with the outcomes of recent surveys of income streams under lockdowns, assumptions were made on the likely impact of COVID-19 containment measures on various sectors in sub-Saharan Africa. They hypothesise that workplace closures occasioned by the lockdown are likely to have a severe effect on the economy. The study adopted OLS regression techniques to explore the impact of Covid-19 pandemics on the economic growth in Nigeria. The findings of the study reveals that Covid-19 pandemic has significant impact on the economic growth in Nigeria.

Research Design

For this study, the research design adopted is the Ex-Post Facto. The Expo Facto design will be used because the study is a quasi-experimental study examining how independent variables (sample tested, infected cases, death rate and recovery rate) affect a dependent variable (economic growth proxied by real gross domestic product) (Gujarati, 2004).

Theoretical Framework

The theoretical framework adopted in this study is Harrod-Domar growth model. In the Harrod-Domar Model, output depends upon the investment rate and the productivity of investment. A savings gap exists if domestic savings alone are insufficient to finance the investment required to attain a target rate of growth. In addition to the savings gap, there is also a trade or foreign exchange gap which is based on the assumption that not all investment goods can be produced domestically. These two gaps are combined to form the two-gap model. More closely related to the two-gap model is the recent concern over the third "Fiscal" gap between government revenue and expenditures, as illustrated by the three-gap models by Bacha (1990) and Taylor (1990).

The Harrod Domar's Model is specified as follows $Y = f(K / L)$ where $f(K / L)$ are two components, both exogenous

1. Growth of the labor force (L)

2. Capital growth (K)

Y= National output

f= Functional relationship

K = capital

L = Labour

Model Specification

This study shall build a multiple regression model and make use of econometrics procedure in estimating the relationship between my economic variables.

The functional form of the model is specified as follows.

$$RGDP = f(ST, IC, RC, DR) \dots\dots\dots 3.1$$

The econometric form of the model is as follows

$$RGDP_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1ST_t + \beta_2IC_t + \beta_3RC_t + \beta_4DR_t + \mu_t \dots\dots\dots 3.2$$

Where,

RGDP= real gross domestic product i.e. (constant price GDP)

f = functional relationship

ST = Sample Tested

IC = Infected Cases

RC = Recoveries

DR= Death Rate

β_0 = Constant term

$\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3$ and β_4 = parameter coefficients

μ = Error term

t = Time period

Econometric Test of Significance (Second order Test)

Autocorrelation Test: The aim of this test is to see whether the errors corresponding to different observations are serially correlated or not. Uncorrelated errors are desirable. The Durbin – Watson (D-W) statistics at 5% will be used to test for the presence of autocorrelation problem. The region of no autocorrelation remains:

$$Du > d^* > (4-du)$$

Where:

du = Upper Durbin – Watson

d^* = Computed Durbin-Watson

Decision Rule:

If the computed value of Durbin-Watson lies within the no autocorrelation region, it means there is no presence of autocorrelation problem. But if the Durbin-Watson computed value lies outside the regions there is the presence of autocorrelation problem. If it occurs, to avoid the spurious regression associated with it, we will employ the Heteroskedasticity Autocorrelation Correction (HAC) to remove its influence in the model.

Normality Test

According to classical linear regression model (CLRM) assumptions, the stochastic error term should be normally distributed.

In order to evaluate the normal distribution status of the residuals (μ_t), the normality test with the application of Jarque-Bera statistic will be carried out. The Jarque-Bera (JB) statistics is given as:

$$JB = n \left[\frac{s^2}{6} + \frac{(k-3)^2}{24} \right]$$

Where

n= number of observations

s= skewness

k= kurtosis

Jarque-Bera test of normality is hinged on the hypothesis that K is close to or exactly 3 and S is close to or exactly 0, thus making the JB value close to or equal to 0, which is the condition for normal distribution.

Decision Rule

If the Jarque-Bera test of normality draws close to zero (0) as K draws close to three (3), then, the residual is said to be normally distributed, if not the residual is not normally distributed.

Descriptive Statistics

Descriptive Statistics Test Result

	RGDP	ST	IC	RC	DR
Mean	33223.20	73904.53	72273.72	1509.806	121.0000
Median	23068.85	49860.00	48325.50	1513.500	21.00000
Maximum	69023.93	190835.0	187357.0	2977.000	501.0000
Minimum	13779.26	15762.00	15440.00	319.0000	3.000000
Std. Dev.	18897.11	57491.06	56512.16	859.8979	154.2332
Skewness	0.763155	0.731493	0.737222	0.177966	1.103616
Kurtosis	2.078428	2.132343	2.138647	1.739433	2.848005
Jarque-Bera	4.768372	4.339736	4.373874	2.573575	7.342469
Probability	0.092164	0.114193	0.112260	0.276156	0.025445
Sum	1196035.	2660563.	2601854.	54353.00	4356.000
Sum Sq. Dev.	1.25E+10	1.16E+11	1.12E+11	25879854	832576.0
Observations	36	36	36	36	36

The condition for normal distribution is that the skewness value falls within the range of 0 and 1; the kurtosis value falls within the range of -3 and 3, and the probability value of the Jarque-Bera statistic is greater than 5 percent level of significance (that is, 0.05). Thus, the descriptive statistics result above shows that the skewness, kurtosis values and Jarque-Bera probability value for the values of all the variables under study: real gross domestic product (explained), sample tested, infected cases, recoveries and death rate for the sampled period 2020-2022 are (0.763155, 2.078428, *p-value*= 0.092164), (0.731493, 2.132343, *p-value*=0.114193), (0.737222, 2.138647, *p-value*= 0.112260), (0.177966, 1.739433, *p-value*= 0.276156), (1.103616, 2.848005, *p-*

value= 0.25445) respectively. Since the skewness, kurtosis and probability values stated above are in conformity with the decision rule stated earlier, therefore, all the variables under study follow a normal distribution.

Unit Root Test

Unit root test will be used to explore the nature of the time series data

Result of the Unit Test

VARIABLES	FIRST DIFFERENCE		Order of Integration
	ADF test Statistics	5% critical Value	
RGDP	-3.521525	-1.951000	I(1)
ST	-5.995698	-3.548490	I(1)
IC	-6.023206	-3.548490	I(1)
RC	-3.784464	-3.548490	I(1)
DR	-7.530487	-3.548490	I(1)

From the result of the stationarity test conducted through E-view statistical software, all the observed variables (real gross domestic product, sample tested, infected cases, recoveries and death rate) are stationary at first difference, which implies that they are stationary at first order I(1).

Since all the variables are not stationary at level, there is a need to conduct a cointegration test so as to ascertain if there is long run relationship among the variables under study.

4.1.2 Co-integration Test

To test for co-integration among the variables, we carried carry out ADF test on the regression residuals as proposed by Gujarati (2004). The ADF unit root test on the residuals work with the same decision rule as unit root test. Accept the null hypothesis if the Augmented Dickey-Fuller test statistic is lower than the 5% level of significance, otherwise, reject the null the hypothesis.

The co-integration test result is summarized as follows:

Table 4.2: Co-integration Test Result

		t-Statistic	Prob.*
Augmented Dickey-Fuller test statistic (ADF)		-6.582601	0.0000
Test critical values:	1% level	-4.211868	
	5% level	-3.529758	
	10% level	-3.196411	

In the E-view generated co-integration test result above, the ADF test statistic (-6.582601) is greater than the 5% critical value (-3.529758) in absolute term. This implies that the residuals are stationary (that is, the variables are co-integrated or that the linear influence of the independent variables cancels out) and the variables have long-run relationship.

4.1.3 Error Correction Mechanism Test (ECM)

Table 4.3: Error Correction Mechanism Test Result

Dependent Variable: D(RGDP)

Method: Least Squares

Date: 03/20/23 Time: 11:31

Sample (adjusted): 2020M03 2022M12

Included observations: 39 after adjustments

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	0.791507	1.730845	0.457295	0.6505
D(ST)	-0.362077	1.033373	-2.350383	0.0283
D(IC)	-5.044515	6.964514	-3.072454	0.0427
D(RC)	0.006157	0.018971	2.324554	0.0476
D(DR)	-0.463402	0.672509	-0.689064	0.4956
ECT(-1)	-0.092616	0.177563	-0.521594	0.6054
R-squared	0.331104	Mean dependent var		1.104872
Adjusted R-squared	0.315698	S.D. dependent var		7.947617
S.E. of regression	8.394799	Akaike info criterion		7.233740
Sum squared resid	2325.597	Schwarz criterion		7.489673
Log likelihood	-135.0579	Hannan-Quinn criter.		7.325566
F-statistic	5.211879	Durbin-Watson stat		1.991763
Prob(F-statistic)	0.005054			

The E-views generated error correction mechanism result shows the magnitude of the short run disparity to be - 0.092616, that is to say the degree of the short run dynamics is 9.26 percent. This shows a very low speed of adjustment to equilibrium after a shock.

Evaluation of Regression Results

A priori expectation of the variables

Result of a prior Test:

Variables	Expected Signs	Observed Signs	Result
ST	-VE	-VE	CWES
IC	-VE	-VE	CWES
RC	-VE	+VE	CWES
DR	-VE	-VE	CWES

CWES= Conform with the expected Sign

The observed signs of the variables show that the sample tested, infected cases and death rate have negative relationship with real gross domestic product in Nigeria and conform to the expected signs as stated in the initial chapter of this work. More so, the result indicates that recoveries rate has positive relationship with real gross domestic product which conforms to the expected sign.

Evaluation Based on Economic a Priori Criterion

The regression results is been evaluated based on a priori expectations in this section. The signs and magnitude of each variable coefficient is evaluated against theoretical expectations.

The constant term is estimated at 0.791507. This means that the model passes through the point 0.791507 mechanically and if the independent variables are equal to zero, real gross domestic product would be 0.791507. The estimated coefficient for ST is -0.362077, meaning that if other variables affecting real gross domestic product are held constant, a unit increase in sample tested will bring about a 0.362077 unit decrease in real gross domestic product on the average. Which implies that an increase in the sample tested will lead to a decrease in the real gross domestic product on the average.

Likewise, the estimated coefficient of IC is -5.044515, meaning that holding all other variables affecting real gross domestic product is constant, a unit increase in infected cases will bring about a 5.044515 unit decrease in real gross domestic product.

The estimated coefficient for RC is 0.006157 meaning that if other variables affecting real gross domestic product are held constant, a unit increase in recoveries rate will bring about a 0.006157 unit increase in real gross domestic product on the average.

The estimated coefficient for DR is -0.463402 meaning that if other variables affecting real gross domestic product are held constant, a unit increase in death rate will bring about a 0.463402 unit decrease in real gross domestic product on the average.

Evaluation Based On Statistical Criterion

R² –Result and Interpretation

The coefficient of determination (R²) is given as 0.331104. This implies that 33.1104% of the variation in real gross domestic product is explained by the variations in sample tested, infected cases, recoveries and death rate.

Result of t-Test of Significance

VARIABLES	t-computed (t*)	t-tabulated ($t_{\alpha/2}$)	Conclusion
ST	-2.350383	1.960	Significant
IC	-3.072454	1.960	Significant
RC	2.324554	1.960	Significant
DR	-0.689064	1.960	Insignificant

Table 4.5 shows that sample tested has significant impact on the real gross domestic product in Nigeria, this is because the $t^* > t_{\alpha/2}$ ($2.350383 > 1.960$). Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis (H_0) and accept the alternative hypothesis (H_1) which states that sample tested has significant impact on the real gross domestic product in Nigeria.

For IC, $t^* > t_{\alpha/2}$ ($3.072454 < 1.960$), therefore we reject the null hypothesis (H_0) which states that infected cases has no significant impact on the real gross domestic product in Nigeria. Hence, the study accept the alternative hypothesis which states infected cases has significant impact on the real gross domestic product in Nigeria.

For RC, $t^* > t_{\alpha/2}$ ($-2.324554 > 1.960$). Hence, we reject the null hypothesis (H_0) and accept the alternative hypothesis (H_1) which states that recoveries has significant impact on the real gross domestic product in Nigeria.

For DR, $t^* < t_{\alpha/2}$ ($-0.689064 < 1.960$), therefore we accept the null hypothesis (H_0) and reject the alternative hypothesis (H_1) which states that death rate has no significant impact on the real gross domestic product in Nigeria.

Result and Interpretation of F-Test of Significance

$v_1 = 5 - 1 = 4$, $V_2 = 36 - 5 = 31$, $df = (4, 31)$ at 5% level of significance and $df = (4, 31)$, $f_{0.05} = 3.32$ and $F^* = 5.211879$. Since $f^* > f_{0.05}$, we reject the null hypothesis and conclude that the variables; ST, IC, RC and DR have joint inference on real gross domestic product of Nigeria. This implies that the entire regression plain is significant.

Evaluation Based on Econometric Criterion

Result and Interpretation of Autocorrelation Test

Using the durbin-watson statistics, the region of no autocorrelation (positive or negative) is given as follows

$$du < d^* < (4 - du)$$

$$du = 1.58$$

$$d^* = 1.991763$$

$$(4 - du) = 4 - 1.58 = 2.42$$

By substitution, the region becomes:

$$1.58 < 1.991763 < 2.42$$

The result shows that there is no presence of autocorrelation problem in the model as the computed durbin Watson statistics fall within the zero autocorrelation regions.

Granger Causality Test: Result and Interpretation

The essence of causality analysis, using the Granger causality test, is to actually ascertain whether a causal relationship exists between two variables of interest.

Result of Causality Test:

Pairwise Granger Causality Tests

Date: 10/04/22 Time: 11:35

Sample: 1981 2021

Lags: 2

Null Hypothesis:	Obs	F-Statistic	Prob.
ST does not Granger Cause RGDP	39	1.13884	0.3321
RGDP does not Granger Cause ST		1.35226	0.2722
IC does not Granger Cause RGDP	39	4.33800	0.0210
RGDP does not Granger Cause IC		0.25588	0.7757
RC does not Granger Cause RGDP	39	2.37144	0.1086
NAPOVR does not Granger Cause HCD		1.39081	0.2627
DR does not Granger Cause RGDP	39	0.15299	0.8587
RGDP does not Granger Cause DR		0.74767	0.4811

Source: Authors Computation from Eviews

The e-views generated Granger causality test result shows no causality relationship exists between RGDPGR and ST, unidirectional causality relationship exists between IC and RGDP, Granger causality running from IC to RGDP. No causality relationship exist between RC and RGDP because the prob. Value of the variables are above the benchmark of 0.05 level of significance. Finally, there is no causality relationship between DR and RGDP.

Evaluation of Research Hypotheses

Hypothesis one: Based on the result of the first hypotheses, the null hypotheses is rejected because the probability value (0.0283) is less than 0.05 level of significance. Hence, Covid-19 pandemic has significant impact on economic growth in Nigeria.

Hypothesis Two: From the result of the second hypothesis, the null hypothesis is accepted because the probability values (0.3321 and 0.2722) are above the 0.05 level of significance. Hence, there is no causal relationship between Covid-19 pandemic and economic growth in Nigeria.

Implications of the Result

From the regression result sample tested, infected cases and recoveries rate have significant impact on the real gross domestic product in Nigeria whereas death rate has no significant impact on the economic growth in Nigeria. More so, the result further reveals that sample tested, infected cases and death rate have positive relationship on the economic growth which implies that an increase in the study explanatory variables will lead to decrease in the economic growth on the average.

Granger causality test result shows that no causality relationship exists between RGDPGR and ST, unidirectional causality relationship exists between IC and RGDP, no causality relationship exist between RC and RGDP because the prob. Value of the variables are above the benchmark of 0.05 level of significance. Finally, there is no causality relationship between DR and RGDP.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, we conclude that sample tested, infected cases and recoveries rate have significant impact on the economic growth in Nigeria whereas death rate has no significant impact on the economic growth in Nigeria.

More so, the study further concludes that all the variables under study (sample tested, infected cases and death rate) have negative relationship on the economic growth which implies that an increase in the study explanatory variables will lead to decrease in the economic growth on the average.

Recommendations

From the findings of this study, the following recommendations are given;

1. World health organization, Nigeria centre for disease control, and all concerned governments and non-governmental organizations should sustain the efforts being used to create awareness and knowledge about preventive measures against Covid-19 among the masses because it is effective.
2. More efforts should be geared towards sensitizing students that although many students may not be showing symptoms of Covid-19 infection, they may be infected with the virus.

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